

SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING ON CLIMATE CHANGE IN THE FORESTRY-BASED INDUSTRY

Atanas Atanasov, Romyana Marinova

Abstract: In recent years, sustainability reporting in the forestry-based industry has gained significant attention, particularly with regard to climate change. Our study synthesizes current research to provide insights into the key themes surrounding sustainability reporting practices specific to climate change mitigation and adaptation in the forestry-based industry. Based on recent publications that explore climate change-related risks and opportunities in the forest industry, our study provides insight into how sustainability reporting can be useful in addressing climate-related risks by providing structured financial and non-financial information about enterprises in the forest sector to different stakeholders. The identified challenges and future directions offer valuable insights for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners working towards a more sustainable and resilient forestry sector in the face of climate change.

Keywords: sustainability reporting, forest-based industry, climate change, risks, sustainability standards

1. INTRODUCTION

Sustainability reporting on climate change in the forestry-based industry is a critical aspect of addressing environmental challenges and ensuring the long-term viability of forest resources. The forestry sector plays a pivotal role in sustainable development, particularly in the urgent context of mitigating climate change (Martinho & Ferreira, 2020). Climate change impacts are not only limited to environmental aspects but also have socio-economic implications, such as community development and rural livelihoods.

The answer to all contemporary challenges lies in providing adequate information on sustainability in forest-based industry enterprises through the application of sustainability reporting. In light of the growing focus on sustainability, there is a need for improved reporting mechanisms to assess the impacts of forestry activities on climate change and the reverse impacts as well.

The importance of forestry-based industry in the EU can be summarized in numbers from CEPI's report: 420 000 enterprises with a total turnover of over 520 billion euros (around 18 % of the bioeconomy), around 3.5 million workers, 143 billion euros each year added value to the economy of European Union (CEPI, 2019).

The aim of this study is based on recent publications that explore climate change-related risks and opportunities in the forest industry to provide insights into the key themes of sustainability reporting practices specific to climate change mitigation and its adaptation in the forestry-based industry. The main thesis we share is that the definition of common indicators for all enterprises and specific sustainability indicators (KPI) in different sectors makes it possible to establish comparability of the reported information and opportunities for making management decisions at the company and national level.

The study focuses mainly on the applicability of legislation in the European Union regarding the reporting of climate-related risks and its application in forestry-based enterprises.

2. CLIMATE CHANGE-RELATED RISKS IN FORESTRY-BASED INDUSTRY

According to a report by the European Forest Institute forests and timber commodities form an integral part of the Land Use, Land-Use Change, and Forestry (LULUCF) sector, a sector within the EU that eliminates around 10% of the total greenhouse gas emissions of the European Union, which currently stand at 256 MtCO₂eq/year. The sector is required to eliminate an additional 50 MtCO₂eq/year by 2030 and 170 MtCO₂eq/year by 2050, as per the policy targets proposed by the European Commission (Verkerk et al., 2022). The analysis in the study indicates that the combined additional mitigation potential achievable by avoiding deforestation, afforestation/reforestation, altering wood utilization, and cascading could reach up to 72 MtCO₂eq/year by 2050 in the EU (Verkerk et al., 2022). At the same time, the CEPI's study indicates that the EU's sustainably managed forests produce today an overall climate mitigation impact amounting to 13 % of European greenhouse gas emissions (CEPI, 2019). According to World Bank Report for 2023 deforestation remains a key source of GHG emissions. Countries included in this report cover 56 percent of the world's tropical forest area and 48 percent of global emissions connected to forest loss. (World Bank Group, 2023).

Forestry-based industries are indeed facing significant climate change-related risks that can impact their operations and sustainability. According to Andersson et al. climate change can lead to various challenges such as changes in forest composition, increased frequency of extreme weather events like storms and wind throw, and alterations in the geographic distribution of tree species (Andersson et al., 2018). These risks are not uniform and can vary by region, with specific geographic areas experiencing different effects of climate change on forestry (Mozgeris et al., 2019).

Adapting to climate change in forestry requires a multifaceted approach that considers both risks and opportunities created by climate change. Furthermore, the forestry industry must focus on sustainable forest management practices that take into account the ecological impacts of climate change and incorporate additional complexities for managers (Álvarez-Miranda et al., 2019). In light of these challenges, there is a growing recognition of the need for enhanced reporting of climate change adaptation in the forestry sector. This includes developing sector-specific sustainability reporting standards and their adoption not only for large public enterprises but for small enterprises too. It is critically important because there is a consensus on the importance of forestry in mitigating climate change through practices like forest carbon sequestration, which can have a significant impact on reducing greenhouse gas emissions.

According to "EU Forest-Based Industries 2050" (CEPI, 2019) mitigation strategies within the forestry sector encompass the prolongation of carbon sequestration in harvested wood products, the practice of product substitution, and the cultivation of biomass for bio-energy purposes. The report indicates that the European forests and the forest-based sector provide integrated solutions to the global climate challenge on a very large scale. The overall and positive climate effect is estimated at -806 million tons of carbon dioxide equivalents annually. This corresponds to c. 20 % of all fossil emissions in the European Union (CEPI, 2019).

Overall, the forestry-based industry faces a range of climate change-related risks that necessitate proactive adaptation strategies, sustainable management practices, and a deeper

**GREEN DEAL INITIATIVES, SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT, MARKET DEMANDS,
AND NEW PRODUCTION PERSPECTIVES IN THE FORESTRY-BASED SECTOR**

understanding of the complex interactions between climate change and forestry ecosystems. All the incentives for climate-related risks mitigation need real-time, adequate and financial-related sustainability information using sustainability reporting.

3. SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING FOR CLIMATE-RELATED RISKS IN FORESTRY-BASED INDUSTRY

Climate change presents significant risks to the forestry-based industry, affecting various aspects of sustainability reporting. Challenges faced by the forestry sector include biodiversity loss, extreme weather events, and the necessity for adaptation due to climate change (Perunová & Zimmermannová, 2022). The implementation of sustainability reporting in small and medium enterprises is important because, as Mikkilä & Toppinen remarked, the social and environmental reporting in large companies is more institutionalized with little flexibility for company-specific diversification in reporting (Mikkilä & Toppinen, 2008).

At the European Union level, the maintenance of sustainability standards (including limits, methodologies, and thresholds) is extensively applied to various countries and regions with diverse levels of representation, aiming to advance the socio-economic roles of forests within the EU (Pecurul-Botines et al., 2023). This effort is guided by the new EU Forest Strategy, which primarily aligns with the objectives outlined in the European Green Deal.

In April 2021, the Sustainable Finance Package was embraced by the European Union with a primary emphasis on bolstering private investments geared towards fostering a climate-resilient economy. This comprehensive package encompasses a proposition for the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD). As a part of the Green Deal in EU Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) and related European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) have a key role in providing information on sustainability issues that is comparable, verifiable, timely and tied to the company's financial performance. According to the rules of the Directive, companies are mandated to provide in-depth and comprehensive disclosures on sustainability performance and the strategic implications involved.

According to the Directive, firms are obligated to evaluate the significance of sustainability issues throughout their value chains and determine which of over 1,000 data points should be revealed. Additionally, disclosures will include qualitative data, such as how corporate strategies address sustainability risks and opportunities. All disclosed information must undergo independent assurance, commencing at a limited level and become reasonable in the future.

The European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS) dictate the disclosures that companies must make. These standards, specific to sustainability reporting within the EU, encompass a wide range of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) topics, such as climate change, biodiversity, and human rights. ESRS aim to facilitate a clear and coherent structure for sustainability information that will be reportable in the sustainability report of the company.

Companies are required to disclose information regarding the business model and strategy with addressing risks linked to sustainability issues, as well as the strategies in place to steer the company toward a sustainable economy and in alignment with the Paris Agreement's objective of limiting global warming to 1.5 °C. This includes the commitment to achieving climate neutrality by 2050. Moreover, companies must provide details on the set

**GREEN DEAL INITIATIVES, SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT, MARKET DEMANDS,
AND NEW PRODUCTION PERSPECTIVES IN THE FORESTRY-BASED SECTOR**

targets associated with sustainability concerns, including specific deadlines for their accomplishment such as GHG emissions reduction targets for 2030 and 2050. Furthermore, they should report on the progress made towards these targets and indicate whether their environmental objectives are founded on scientific evidence.

The main requirements for reporting climate change–related risks and information are described in ESRS E1 – *Climate Change*. This standard will be mandatory for all forestry-based enterprises within the scope of the Directive. ESRS E1 is one of the topical standards that aims to specify Disclosure Requirements that will enable users of sustainability statements to understand (ESRS E1, 2023):

- how the undertaking affects climate change, in terms of material positive and negative actual and potential impacts
- the undertaking’s past, current, and future mitigation efforts in line with the Paris Agreement (or an updated international agreement on climate change) and limiting global warming to 1.5°C;
- the plans and capacity of the undertaking to adapt its strategy business model(s) and in line with the transition to a sustainable economy and to contribute to limiting global warming to 1.5°C;
- any other actions taken by the undertaking, and the result of such actions to prevent, mitigate or remediate actual or potential negative impacts
- the nature, type and extent of the undertaking’s material risks and opportunities arising from the undertaking’s impacts and dependencies on climate change, and how the undertaking manages them
- the financial effects on the undertaking over the short, medium and long-term time horizons of risks and opportunities arising from the undertaking’s impacts and dependencies on climate change.

ESRS E1 also formulates 9 distinct disclosure requirements which makes this standard highly structured (from E 1-1 to E 1-9). All these requirements are divided into three main groups: Strategy (E1-1), Impact, risk and opportunity management (E1-2, E1-3) and Metrics and targets (E1-4 to E 1-9). Based on the information above and because the CSRD is one of the elements of the European Green Deal, which aims to make the European Union carbon neutral by 2050, and to keep global warming to 1.5 degrees, in line with the objectives of the Paris Agreement, we share the view that ESRS E1 probably will be the standard on which the greatest efforts will be focused. This standard is “special” because if the company determines that reporting on ESRS E1 is unnecessary, a comprehensive and well-reasoned justification must be presented, along with an examination of potential future circumstances that may warrant the topic being deemed “material”.

Each Disclosure Requirement is linked to an Application Requirement, particularly in the case of ESRS E1. These specifications outline in great detail the necessary responses that companies must provide to the various inquiries presented to them. When addressing the accountability of their greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, companies are obligated to adhere to the methodology established by the GHG Protocol and gather data on the scope 1, 2, and 3 aspects of their operations. As previously mentioned, the computation of emissions pertains to their entire value chain. This can prove to be a considerably intricate task, necessitating the involvement of numerous stakeholders, ranging from employees to suppliers and service providers.

**GREEN DEAL INITIATIVES, SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT, MARKET DEMANDS,
AND NEW PRODUCTION PERSPECTIVES IN THE FORESTRY-BASED SECTOR**

In addition to merely assessing GHG emission levels and the environmental impact of their operations, forestry-based organizations must also incorporate this data into their corporate strategies. Within section E 1-3 of ESRS E1, companies are expected to elaborate on each action taken throughout the year to mitigate and/or adapt to climate change, along with the achieved outcomes and anticipated results. Specifically, this report should encompass all initiatives aimed at climate change mitigation through decarbonization and efforts to diminish GHG emissions.

Moreover, in section E 1-4, companies should outline all actions taken during the year to address climate change, as well as the accomplished results and expected outcomes. Particularly, this presentation should encompass all strategies related to climate change mitigation through decarbonization and measures to reduce GHG emissions.

For the most part, climate-related risks have their financial dimensions in company reports. The E 1-9 Disclosure Requirement of ESRS E1 focuses entirely on evaluating the projected financial impacts (risks and/or opportunities) of climate change and the execution of a transition plan. This evaluation demands the full integration of climate considerations into corporate strategies. Companies must demonstrate their anticipation of the impacts of climate change on their operations and the measures taken to address them.

Incorporating measures to reduce their environmental footprint must also be a part of this strategic approach. Consequently, forestry-based companies will need to establish GHG emission reduction targets aligned with the objectives of the Paris Agreements, which seek to limit global warming to 1.5°C, and the European goal of achieving carbon neutrality by 2050.

4. CONCLUSION

Sustainability reporting on climate-related risks is essential for improving decision-making processes within organizations. We support the view that integrating climate risk disclosures into sustainability reports enhances environmental accountability and transparency. These disclosures offer valuable information on both mitigating and adapting to climate risks, enabling stakeholders to make well-informed decisions. The increasing recognition of climate change among various stakeholders motivates corporations to improve transparency in sustainability data, assess operational efficiency, and enhance environmental, social, and governance practices.

By redefining the materiality concept to include climate-related risks, utilizing decision-support tools, and integrating sustainability indicators, forestry-based companies can make informed decisions that contribute to sustainable development goals. The challenges that have been identified and the future directions that have been outlined provide valuable perspectives for researchers, policymakers, and practitioners who are dedicated to advancing the forestry sector that is both sustainable and resilient amidst the challenges posed by climate change.

REFERENCES

1. Álvarez-Miranda, E., Garcia-Gonzalo, J., Pais, C., & Weintraub, A. (2019). A multicriteria stochastic optimization framework for sustainable forest decision making under uncertainty. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 103, 112-122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2018.03.006>

**GREEN DEAL INITIATIVES, SUSTAINABLE MANAGEMENT, MARKET DEMANDS,
AND NEW PRODUCTION PERSPECTIVES IN THE FORESTRY-BASED SECTOR**

2. Álvarez-Miranda, E., García-Gonzalo, J., Pais, C., & Weintraub, A. (2019). A multicriteria stochastic optimization framework for sustainable forest decision making under uncertainty. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 103, 112-122. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2018.03.006>
3. Andersson, E., Keskkitalo, E., & Bergstén, S. (2018). In the eye of the storm: adaptation logics of forest owners in management and planning in Swedish areas. *Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research*, 33(8), 800-808. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02827581.2018.1494305>
4. CEPI. (2019, 11). https://www.cepi.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/Cepi-Climate-effects-of-the-forest-based-sector-in-the-EU_Exc-summary.pdf. Retrieved from CEPI: https://www.cepi.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/06/Cepi-Climate-effects-of-the-forest-based-sector-in-the-EU_Exc-summary.pdf
5. ESRS E1. (2023). ESRS E1 Climate Change. Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/2772 of 31 July 2023 supplementing Directive 2013/34/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards sustainability reporting standards. OJ L, 2023/2772, 22.12.2023. EC. Retrieved from http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg_del/2023/2772/oj
6. Martinho, V. J. P. D. and Ferreira, A. J. D. (2020). Forest Resources Management and Sustainability: The Specific Case of European Union Countries. *Sustainability*, 13(1), 58. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13010058>
7. Mikkilä, M. and Toppinen, A. (2008). Corporate responsibility reporting by large pulp and paper companies. *Forest Policy and Economics*, 10(7-8), 500-506. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.forpol.2008.05.002>
8. Mozgeris, G., Brukas, V., Pivoriūnas, N., Činga, G., Makrickiene, E., Byčenkienė, S., ... & Augustaitis, A. (2019). Spatial pattern of climate change effects on Lithuanian forestry. *Forests*, 10(9), 809. <https://doi.org/10.3390/f10090809>
9. Pecurul-Botines, M., Secco, L., Bouriaud, L., Giurca, A., Brockhaus, M., Brukas, V., Hoogstra-Klein, M.A., Konczal, A., Marcinekova, L., Niedzialkowski, K., Øistad, K., Pezdevšek Malovrh, Š., Pietarinen, N., Roux, J-L., Wolfslehner, B., Winkel, G. 2023. Meeting the European Union's Forest Strategy goals: A comparative European assessment. *From Science to Policy 15*. European Forest Institute. <https://doi.org/10.36333/fs15>
10. Perunová, M. and Zimmermannová, J. (2022). Analysis of forestry employment within the bioeconomy labor market in the Czech Republic. *Journal of Forest Science*, 68(10), 385-394. <https://doi.org/10.17221/84/2022-jfs>
11. Verkerk, P.J., Delacote, P., Hurmekoski, E., Kunttu, J., Matthews, R., Mäkipää, R., Mosley, F., Perugini, L., Reyer, C. P. O., Roe, S., Trømborg, E. 2022. Forest-based climate change mitigation and adaptation in Europe. *From Science to Policy 14*. European Forest Institute. <https://doi.org/10.36333/fs14>
12. World Bank Group. (2023). *The Development, Climate, and Nature Crisis: Solutions to End Poverty on a Livable Planet*. Washington: The World Bank Group.

Authors address:

Atanasov, A.¹; Marinova, R.²

^{1,2} Accounting Department, University of Economics – Varna, Bulgaria

*Corresponding author: atanasov_at@ue-varna.bg